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By Stud. med. vet Anne Bach Bjarre

Behavioural indices related to pain before and after extraction of teeth in horses diagnosed with Equine odontoclastic tooth resorption and hypercementosis (EOTRH)

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Title and subtitle: Behavioural indices related to pain before and after extraction of teeth in horses diagnosed with equine odontoclastic tooth resorption and hypercementosis (EOTRH)

Topic description: The aim of the study is to prove that horses with Equine Odontoclastic Tooth Resorption and Hypercementosis (EOTRH) feel pain, and the pain decreases after extraction of the affected teeth. This is investigated by the use of questionnaires, observations of behavioural changes, and evaluation of Equine Pain Face (EPF) and Horse Grimace Scale (HGS)

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study is to investigate behavioural changes in horses prior and post extraction of teeth affected by Equine Odontoclastic Tooth Resorption and Hypercementosis (EOTRH), and to evaluate if facial expressions of pain can be recognised after making the horse bite a carrot. The evaluations are performed using the Equine Pain Face (EPF) and the Horse Grimace Scale (HGS).

Study design: A retrospective cohort study in correspondence with a prospective cohort study of the behavioural changes before and after surgery. The prospective study includes an observational study and a blinded evaluation of facial expressions of pain performed by an expert and a trained veterinarian.

Animals: 47 horses included in the retrospective study and 12 horses included in the prospective study.

Materials and methods: Questionnaires regarding the behavioural changes prior and post surgery. The prospective study also includes an observation of the horses one to seven days before extraction and between six and eight weeks after extraction of the affected teeth. While being observed and filmed the horses are asked to off a carrot. Sequences from the recordings are used at the blinded evaluation of pain faces.

Results: The horses had an increase in positive behaviour after the surgery with significant differences in both the retrospective study ($p=6,27*10^{-9}$) and the prospective study ($p=0,0024$). The prevalence of EPF significantly decreases from 64% prior to 18% post surgery ($p=0,05$). HGS scored $2,8 \pm 2,2$ and $1,4 \pm 1,4$ from before to after extraction, respectively, with significant change ($p=0,03$), but only six horses was included in this evaluation.

Conclusion and clinical relevance: This study shows that horses have increased positive behaviour after extraction of teeth affected by EOTRH, and that many horses display pain face, when forced to use their front teeth prior to surgery. EOTRH should be acknowledged as a painful disease and veterinarians should consider this disease, if they observe unspecific decrease in welfare in geriatric horses.

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Introduction

Equine Odontoclastic Tooth Resorption and Hypercementosis (EOTRH) is a relatively recent acknowledged disease in aging horses (Klugh, 2004)(Staszyk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008). The prevalence is estimated to range from 63%-92% in horses above 10 years (Rehrl, Schröder, Müller, Staszyk, & Lischer, 2018).

The clinical signs of the disease are numerous in concern of the incisors in the late stages, but can also non-specific and vague, why the disease is often recognised before the horse has its normal dental examination (Staszyk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008) (Kreutzer, Wohlsein, Staszyk, Nowak, Sill, & Buamgärtner, 2007) (Henry & Griffin, 2017).

The disease is described as painful, but there has not been any studies conducted on describing the pain. EOTRH is a slowly developing disease and the pain is therefore considered to be chronic.

To describe pain in animals changes behaviour is often the used and assessed in different composite (measure) pain scales (Gleerup & Lindegaard, 2016).

The aim of this study was to determine if EOTRH is painful and if the horse increases its quality of life post extraction of the affected teeth based on the behavioural changes.

Theory

Equine Odontoclastic Tooth Resorption and Hypercementosis (EOTRH)

The clinical signs of EOTRH is first described by Klugh in 2004 as an uncommon or under – recognised disease of the incisor and canine teeth in aged horses. It is described as a periodontal disease caused by inflammation to the periodontal ligament due to feed stasis in geriatric horses as a consequence of the reduced range of motion caused by elongated teeth combined with a reduced production of saliva due to hard feed such as hay and grain. The saliva and range of motion help clean the mouth and reduce the gingivitis and periodontitis. Klugh (2004) also describes changes in the normal mouth flora resulting in bacterial infections as part of the pathogenesis.

Staszyk et al named the disease in 2008. Here the periodontitis is described as occasional and the changes in the calcified dental tissue as resorptive or proliferative (Staszyk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008).

The clinical signs of the disease are seen as calculus, gingival retraction and thereby exposure of the reserve crown, gingival ulcerations, purulent periodontitis, fistulae, tooth mobility and deformation of the bone structure. When clinical signs become obvious, the process of resorption has been on-going for a significant period of time. The time frame of the disease is not yet established.

Figure 1: Picture of a horse at a clinical examination. The horse has extensive calculus, gingival retraction, deformation of the bone structure and the teeth are displaced because of tooth mobility.

To diagnose the disease radiographic examination is required. The radiographic findings of EOTRH can be divided in to two different categories; dental resorption and bulbous enlargement of the reserve crown and root. Additional findings are loss of periodontal space, widening of the periodontal ligament, tooth fractures, osteomyelitis, lack of lamina dura, and disruption of alveolar bone. The findings are not identical with all horses (Staszyk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008) (Kreutzer, Wohlsein, Staszyk, Nowak, Sill, & Buamgärtner, 2007) (Henry & Griffin, 2017). The radiographic changes need to be distinguished from geriatric changes such as widening of the periodontal ligament, blunting of the apices, alveolar sclerosis and loss of alveolar bone (Hole & Staszyk, 2018).

Figure 2: Display of incisors affected by equine odontoclastic tooth resorption and hypercementosis. 1: Normal incisor 2: Incisor with resorption on the reserve crown 3: Resorption of the reserve crown spreading to the crown 4: Hypercementosis and resorption of the root and reserve crown 5-7: Different appearances of hypercementosis

Histopathological findings show inflammatory cells, fibrosis of the gingival and periodontal ligaments and focal lysis of the adjacent alveolar bone, as well as resorption and hypercementosis.

The resorptive lesions extend from the peripheral cementum into enamel, dentine or pulp. The lesions are spread in the periapical region; often the areas with the greatest resorption are the middle third of the reserve crown. The lesions may have totally destroyed the architecture of the teeth. There are remnants of normal dentine and cementum mixed with irregular cementum and necrotic tissue. In the mid and subgingival areas, the lesions are a mixture of the irregular cementum and granulation tissue. The surface lesions show focal lining of multinucleated odontoclasts, which are causing the resorption. These lesions are named resorption lacunae or Howship's lacunae. The pulp is only affected by external resorption. Internal resorption, which is initiated in the pulp, is not seen. The resorption often affects all the incisors and progress from the third to the first (Triadan system) over time (Staszuk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008) (Smedley, Earley, Galloway, Baratt, & Rawlinson, 2015).

Bulbous enlargement of the roots consists of rough calcified deposits described as an irregular form of cementum. The teeth covered with irregular cementum either keep their normal architecture or it is lost and exchanged with necrotic tissue. The deposit of cementum is not only seen at the focal resorption place, as there is also irregular hypercementosis around un-resorbed normal cementum. The new cementum provides reattachment to the periodontal ligament through collagen fibres from the ligament. The teeth affected by hypercementosis are often not affected by fistulae (Staszuk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008) (Kreutzer,

Wohlsein, Staszuk, Nowak, Sill, & Buamgärtner, 2007) (Baratt, 2011) (Smedley, Earley, Galloway, Baratt, & Rawlinson, 2015).

The aetiology of the disease is still unknown. Diseases similar to EOTRH in horses are found in humans and cats, termed Idiopathic Root Resorption and Hypercementosis or Multiple Idiopathic Root Resorption (MIRR) and Feline Odontoclastic Resorptive Lesions (FORL). In humans and cats the periodontal ligament initialises the process by releasing factors to initiate odontoclastic activity, which causes external resorption. Secondly, fibroblasts and cementoblasts invade to repair the resorbed surface. The repair in humans differs from the equine form by a limited response of the formation of cement and therefore hypercementosis only occurs in horses (Reiter & Mendoza, 2002) (Schätzle & Bosshardt, 2005) (DeLaurier, Boyde, Jackson, Horton, & Price, 2009).

The increased stress on the periodontal ligament due to the forces applied when mastication caused by the reduced dental-periodontal surface in aged horses, is suggested as a potential cause for starting a necrotic reaction that later initiates the external resorption. This does not explain the involvement of the canine teeth, which is seen in a number of cases, since these are not an active part of the mastication. However, the masticatory forces create stress and strain along the mandible, which runs into the periodontal area of the canines and thereby affect these teeth. The aetiology is considered to be multifactorial, where causes like periodontal disease, genetics, trauma, hormonal conditions, low mastication time, hypervitaminosis A, other unknown diseases and pathogens with the potential to cause periodontal infections, may be involved (Staszuk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008) (Pearson, Mansfield, Conaway, & Koput, 2013) (Hole & Staszuk, 2018)).

Periodontal disease is commonly associated with EOTRH, and it is clear that EOTRH can cause severe periodontal infection. The inflammation caused by periodontal disease destroys the normal structure of the tooth, but treating the periodontal disease will not stop the development of EOTRH (Rawlinson & Earley, 2013) (Baratt R. M., 2007)).

Bacterial infections seem to be secondary, since the infection begins in the gingival lesions and areas, where the stress and strain of aging teeth create the necrotic foci. These foci provide a rich environment for these microorganisms to live and multiply (Baratt R. M., 2007) (Hole & Staszuk, 2018). One study has shown the presence of *Treponema* and *Tannerella* spp. in all of the diseased horses. However, the control group had a prevalence of 52,2% of the same bacteria. Therefore, the immune status of the individual horse is likely to be an important factor (Sykora, Pieber, Simhofer, Hackl, Brodesser, & Brandt, 2014).

Trauma to the teeth caused by excessive dentistry and periodontal diseases seem to lead to a five-fold increase in the risk of later developing of EOTRH.

Low mastication time might also increase the risk since the saliva is an active part when it comes to reducing risk of periodontal diseases (Pearson, Mansfield, Conaway, & Koput, 2013).

Horses with pituitary pars intermedia dysfunction (PPID) and equine metabolic syndrome (EMS) are considered more predisposed to infections. It is also indicated in canine Cushing's disease that the prevalence of ligament laxity is increased, because of the higher level of cortisol, which may lead to a higher risk of developing EOTRH (Pearson, Mansfield, Conaway, & Koput, 2013). Since the aetiology is multifactorial, it is difficult to prove the exact pathogenesis. The influence of mastication and involvement of microorganisms in periodontitis are in complete accordance with the histopathological findings, whereas the rest of the proposed factors still need further investigation in order to determine these factors' specific involvement in the pathogenesis (Hole & Staszuk, 2018).

EOTRH is often described as a painful disease, which is also a reasonable assumption given the very severe dental and osseous lesion seen in these patients. Furthermore, pain is considered to be increasing with an increase in the severity of the disease. Owners often report that their first sign is the horse's lacking ability to bite off carrots or apples (Earley & Rawlinson, 2013). Other signs reported from owners are weight loss, changes in mastication, un-localized pain and behavioural changes. Despite these signs the disease is often discovered, when the horse has its regularly dental examination (Lorello, Foster, G, Boyle, & Orsini, 2016) (Earley & Rawlinson, 2013).

There is no known treatment to the disease. Several possibilities have been suggested, but none of them have been able to cure the disease. Consequently, the treatment of choice is extraction of the affected teeth (Staszuk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008 (Hole & Staszuk, 2018)).

There are several techniques to extract the teeth going from surgical removal in general anaesthesia to standing extraction. The mucosa is either closed or left open. Post-operative treatment includes treatment nothing but nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) and antibiotics are generally not indicated (Baratt R. , 2011) (Lorello, Foster, G, Boyle, & Orsini, 2016) (Rawlinson & Earley, 2013).

Even after the extraction of the affected teeth the progression of the EOTRH will continue if any incisors and perhaps canine teeth are left. Therefore, it is necessary to continue visual and radiological examinations, as well as determining the equids' signs of pain, to determine the

number of further teeth to be extracted and when to do so. The decision of leaving some teeth should be made in consideration of the status of the teeth and individual owner's ability to evaluate the progression of the disease (Rawlinson & Earley, 2013) (Henry & Griffin, 2017) (Lorello, Foster, G, Boyle, & Orsini, 2016).

Post extraction, feed material will adhere to and become entrapped at the extraction site, yet still the extraction sockets will heal quickly and are often covered by gingiva three weeks after extraction (Baratt, 2011).

After extraction of the affected teeth, the horse quickly adapts to its new dental setup, and most often it is able to masticate well, even when all the incisors are removed (Henry & Griffin, 2017). In horses where all 12 incisors are extracted, reports of the horse's tongue hanging from the mouth are found. In some horses this is only seen, when they are relaxed and in others at all times. There are no records of continued oral/dental problems with the bit or the return to prior use after the convalescence period (Lorello, Foster, G, Boyle, & Orsini, 2016).

The vast majority of horses affected with EOTRH are middle-aged to geriatric with reported ages from fourteen to twenty-nine at the time of diagnosis. Furthermore, there is a tendency that male horses are more often affected than mares. It is more often mandibular incisors than maxillary incisors, and the canine teeth are rarely affected (Lorello, Foster, G, Boyle, & Orsini, 2016) (Rahmani, Häyrynen, Kareinen, & Ruohoniemi, 2019). A breed specific predisposition is still undocumented (Rehrl, Schröder, Müller, Staszuk, & Lischer, 2018). One study shows that all equids above 14 years of age, included in this specific study, has radiological signs of EOTRH and every horse above 28 years of age has moderate changes of the incisors; therefore, one must consider that mild changes are associated with the normal dental ageing process. The overall prevalence of EOTRH in horses above 10 years of age, presented at the Equine Hospital of the Freie universität Berlin for routine dental examination over a three year period are somewhere between 62,0% and 93,7% (Rehrl, Schröder, Müller, Staszuk, & Lischer, 2018).

Pain physiology

Pain is a multidimensional sensory and emotional experience, which causes the individual to become more aware and change behavioural in order to protect the body against tissue damage. The neural process in pain is called nociception and includes the transduction, transmission, modulation and central processing of the received stimuli (mechanical, chemical, thermal or electrical). The cutaneous stimuli have to be of a certain threshold to result in a reaction. The noxious stimuli are conducted to action potentials, which are transmitted to the spinal cord by

primary afferent nerve fibres. In the spinal cord they are connected to secondary nerve fibres, and the input modulated through various enhancing and inhibitory processes, after which the action potentials are conducted to the brain. In the brain the stimuli are projected and then finally perceived as pain in the cerebral cortex.

If the stimuli are sufficient to cause tissue damage and inflammation, the pain will persist and nociception adapt (or maladapt) to facilitate healing. Various substances produced during inflammation and tissue damage enhance nociception, leading to hyperalgesia and allodynia. Horses with untreated or chronic painful diseases, which are maladaptive, may lead to neural and endocrine responses, influencing the homeostatic hormonal functions (Muir, 2010).

Pain lasting more than three months has been defined as chronic pain. Furthermore, it has to occur at least 50% of the days during the 3 months and last 2 hours per day. Dental pain originates from the teeth or the related tissues such as pulpa, gingiva or periapical tissue. Dental pain is known to have an impact on daily activities in humans (Benoliel, et al., 2019). Chronic pain can persist beyond the healing process; therefore, horses in chronic pain might experience pain even after removal of the cause and/or healing of the affected area (McLennan, et al., 2019).

Equine pain

According to the International Association for the Study of Pain, pain is defined as “*An unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with, or resembling that associated with, actual or potential tissue damage,*” and is expanded upon by the addition of six key Notes and the etymology of the word pain for further valuable context.

- *Pain is always a personal experience that is influenced to varying degrees by biological, psychological, and social factors.*
- *Pain and nociception are different phenomena. Pain cannot be inferred solely from activity in sensory neurons.*
- *Through their life experiences, individuals learn the concept of pain.*
- *A person’s report of an experience as pain should be respected.*
- *Although pain usually serves an adaptive role, it may have adverse effects on function and social and psychological well-being.*
- *Verbal description is only one of several behaviors to express pain; inability to communicate does not negate the possibility that a human or a nonhuman animal experiences pain.” (IASP Taskforce for the Classification of Pain, 2020).*

As human beings we rely a lot on our verbal communication, including when we evaluate pain. This is not a possibility when evaluating pain in animals and non-verbal humans, why

observations of silent communication such as behavioural changes and facial expression become necessary.

In general pain in animals can in general lead to behavioural changes such as stress, reduced play, disrupted sleep, as well as reduced grooming and changes while it is eating. Horses may also express pain as anxiety, depression, lameness, stomping, rolling and increased/ decreased social interactions (McLennan, et al., 2019) (Muir, 2010).

It is impossible for the observer to sum up the sensory and emotional experiences of a horse. Therefore, the only way we can try to evaluate and quantify their pain is to analyse their behaviour and facial expressions. It should be noted that pain evaluation in horses is further complicated by the fact that horses are prey animals and therefore tend to hide signs of pain to avoid predation, especially when the pain is mild to moderate pain. The fact that they hide their signs is also evident in the presence of caretakers (de Grauw & van Loon, 2016) (Torvicia & McDonnell, 2020).

The reported behavioural changes in horses experiencing dental pain may include headshaking, slow eating, changed head position and abnormal mastication, caused by a decreased range of motion (Dixon & Dacre, 2005). It has to be noted that these reported behavioural changes are observed in horses with problems of the premolars and molars, which are used for grinding the food, explaining why many of the symptoms are related to the digestion of food. These behavioural changes do not point towards a specific diagnosis, but indicate that the mouth may be involved. A study conducted on pain related to the cheek teeth concluded that the behavioural changes associated with pain were decreased after removal of the affected tooth/teeth. The signs described in this specific study include withdrawn or intense stare, asocial behaviour towards people and other horses and aggressive behaviour. The authors mention that the gaze may be what other associate with one of the facial expression related to pain (Pehkonen, J, Karma, & Raekallio, 2019).

Since 2008 EOTRH has been described as a painful disease (Staszuk, Bienert, Kreutzer, Wohlsein, & Simhofer, 2008). There are no studies conducted on the subject, why this statement must rely on the authors' own experiences. Pain associated with EOTRH is believed to be chronic due to the slow progressive nature of the disease leading to a protracted course of the disease prior to its diagnosis. The protraction seems to be more than three months. Signs of chronic (dental) pain may be very subtle in horses, which is why owners might miss these changes in the initial phase of the disease (Rahmani, Häyrynen, Kareinen, & Ruohoniemi, 2019).

To evaluate equine pain, several approaches have been proposed. A simple descriptive scale does not seem sufficient when dealing with such a complex entity as equine pain, why several composite (measure) pain scales (CMPS) have been suggested. Many of these CMPSs consist of the same behavioural categories. The behavioural changes described in horses experiencing pain are: loss of appetite, restlessness, depression, abnormal posture, changed weight bearing, pawing, repeated head movements, changes in social interaction, pain face, attention to painful area, and gross pain behaviours (Gleerup & Lindegaard, 2016). These scales are developed for patients with acute pain, often in a hospital setting, and are therefore not necessarily relevant or sufficient for assessment and quantification of chronic pain with horses in their common, every day environment. It is suggested that chronic pain may lead to depression and that the horses become inactive with reduce grooming, appetite and social activity and appear with glassy eyes and lowered head, as well as changes in their posture and responses to handling when feeling pain (Gleerup & Lindegaard, 2016) (de Grauw & van Loon, 2016)(Carstens & Moberg, 2000). It has been reported that facial expressions do not last for more than 48 hours in animals as rats and it is therefore not used to assess chronic pain and that chronic pain in general is more difficult to recognize, even though it is important for the welfare of the horse to identify the pain. (McLennan, et al., 2019) (Carstens & Moberg, 2000). Furthermore, one needs to be aware that clinical evaluation is biased by the perception and philosophy of the observer (Pehkonen, J, Karma, & Raekallio, 2019).

The Equine Pain Face and Horse Grimace Scale

Facial expressions change when people are experiencing pain, even when humans are asked to hide their pain. Therefore, observation of facial expressions is a well-established tool to assess pain, even in neonates and humans with cognitive impairment. These observations have led to the development of pain scales based on facial expressions of various animals (McLennan, et al., 2019), including horses. One scale has been based solely on facial expressions; The Horse Grimace Scale (Dalla Costa, Minero, Lebelt, Stucke, Canali, & Leach, 2014). An equine pain face has also been suggested. "The Equine Pain Face" is based on the exact same facial expressions of pain as HGS, although it is not intended for grading pain in a quantitative manner, but rather intended for early recognition of pain in horses (Gleerup, Forkman, Lindegaard, & Andersen, 2015). The Equine Pain Face is used in "The Equine Pain Scale", where it is combined with other behavioural parameters to a CMPS (Gleerup & Lindegaard, 2016). Both HGS and EPF are developed for use on acute pain. The facial expressions observed and evaluated in these scales are positioning of the ears, eyes and nostrils, muscle tension as well as

the glance of the eyes. The Equine Utrecht University scale for facial assessment of pain (EQUUS-FAP) includes the same facial areas, but do also include behavioural categories such as lip curling and tooth grinding (van Loon & Van Dierendonck, 2019). All the changes are not necessarily present simultaneously and there will be changes in facial expressions when the horse reacts to the surroundings. The horse Grimace Scale is a quantitative scale, using the score 0-2 is used to grade six individual facial features (Dalla Costa, Minero, Lebelt, Stucke, Canali, & Leach, 2014).

One study evaluated the use of the HGS in relation to dental disorders. The study included 33 horses having one to five different disorders each, but there was no description of which disorders were treated. It was found that most of the horses showed signs of pain according to HGS and that most of them scored lower after dental treatment (Coneglian, Borges, Weber, Bertagnon, & Michelotto, 2020).

The EQUUS-FAP has been validated for acute and postoperative pain originating from the head (van Loon & Van Dierendonck, 2017).

Aim

The aim of the study is to determine if EOTRH is painful and if the horse increases its quality of life post extraction of the affected teeth based on behavioural changes. This is done conducting both a retrospective and a prospective study. The retrospective study consists of a questionnaire about behaviour sent to former cases treated for EOTRH. The prospective study is divided into two questionnaires, observations and evaluations of video and stills performed both prior and post extraction of the affected teeth.

Hypothesis

Study 1 Retrospective cases

Hypothesis 1

H_0 = Horses with EOTRH do not have changed behaviour before compared to after extraction of teeth according to their owner.

H_A = Horses with EOTRH have changed behaviour before compared to after extraction according to their owner.

Study 2 Prospective cases

Hypothesis 1

H_0 = Horses with EOTRH do not have changed behaviour before compared to after extraction of teeth according to their owner.

H_A = Horses with EOTRH have changed behaviour before compared to after extraction according to their owner.

Hypothesis 2

H_0 = Horses do not have changes in their facial expressions after eating carrots before compared to after extraction of teeth according to EPF and HGS

H_A = Horses do not have changes in their facial expressions after eating carrots before compared to after extraction of teeth according to EPF and HGS

Material and methods

Type of study and ethical aspect

The study is a cohort study and was approved by the Local Ethical and Administrative Committee of the Department of Veterinary Clinical Science at University of Copenhagen under registration number 2020-015. Owner consent has been obtained for all animals participating.

Horses

To fulfil the aim of the thesis, two studies were conducted, which should make it possible to answer the two hypotheses. The two studies consist of a retrospective study and a prospective study.

The included cases in study one consists of horses which have had the diagnosis EOTRH and therefore have had one or more teeth extracted by a veterinarian from Hestetandklinikken, Ringsted, Denmark between 2016 and 2020.

To be included in the second study the horses should either be from or referred to Hestetandklinikken for extraction of EOTRH affected teeth between the 21st of July and the 26th of October 2020. The horses were excluded if they did not fulfil the criteria of diagnosis after the radiographic exam.

Study design

Study 1

To initiate the study a questionnaire was emailed to owners of horses, who were included by the criteria prior to the start of the study period (Appendix 1.1). Emails were sent to 126 cases. The survey referred to the behaviour of the horses in the field/ stable, during handling and riding and the eating behaviour before and after extraction of the affected teeth. One of the questions asked about the owners' feelings about the procedure and their general opinion about the changes in the welfare of their horses. A single question asked if the horses suffered from other concurrent diseases. The questionnaire was used to conduct a comparison of behaviour before and after extraction, as well as a subjective descriptive analysis.

Study 2

The horses in this study were followed from before extraction until 6 to 8 weeks after.

First visit

The horses were evaluated in their normal habitual environment one to seven days before the extraction of the involved teeth. The observer entered the stable or field quietly, waited until the horses were acclimatized and then filmed the horses' behaviour. The first videos were made with a JVC recording camera, but this was broken, so the rest was made using an iPhone 7. The horses were approached while filming in order to evaluate the horses' response to foreign people. The horses were brought to the stable or grooming site and tied up. When the horses were quiet, they were feed a carrot (2-3 cm in diameter) while filming. The purpose of feeding the horses a carrot were to see how the horses bite off the carrot and the recording was made to observe, if there were any behavioural or facial changes after chewing the carrot. The camera was hand-held trying to focus on the head of the horse at approximately 1-1,5 m distance, attempting not to disturb the horses. The videos are used for later evaluation.

Operation

At the day of the treatment, the horses were either in their own stable or brought to the clinic. A general physical examination of temperature, heart rate and respiration rate was conducted. The horses were evaluated clinically and radiographically, and the decision of which teeth to extract was made by the veterinarian.

The horses were sedated with a loading dose of a mixture of detomidinhydrochlorid (Cepesedan®) and butorphanol (Morphasol®) and thereafter a constant rate infusion of saline with detomidinhydrochlorid (Cepesedan®), butorphanol (Morphasol®) and romifidinhydrochlorid (Sedivet®). The horses had infiltration of n. infraorbitalis, n. mentalis with mepivacainhydrochlorid (Mepidor®) and/or infiltration of the periodontal ligaments with adrenaline and lidocain (Xion®) to cover the pain during the operation. Before the procedure started the horses were given systemic analgesic consisting of intravenous flunixin (Flunixin®). The affected teeth were extracted in toto during standing surgery. After removal the vacated alveoli and gingiva were debrided and left open. Postoperative inflammatory/analgesic therapy consisted of meloxicam (Metacam®) for the five following days. No antimicrobial therapy was given.

Follow up examination

Follow up examination was performed between 14 and 21 days after extraction with the purpose of evaluating the healing process and remove possible sequestrers.

Last visit

The last evaluation of the horses was done six to eight weeks after extraction. Here the horses were observed and filmed in their normal habitual environment again, and the horses were fed carrots or pieces of carrots (the ones without incisors) while filming in order to compare with former recordings of facial expressions and behaviour.

Pain evaluation

To evaluate the pain experienced by the horses in relation to EOTRH we looked at the horses' behaviour and the facial expressions. The behaviour is observed at the first visit, during which general behaviour and responses to approach were noted. At the same time the owners received a questionnaire about their observations of the horses' behaviour, which was to be answered before the extraction (Appendix 1.2).

At the follow up examination the owners were asked about their first reactions to the fitness and behaviour of their horses.

The horses were observed again at the last visit and a new questionnaire was given. This questionnaire included a question, asking the owners to evaluate the general changes of his or her horse (Appendix 1.3). The questionnaires were used to conduct a comparison of behaviour before and after extraction, as well as a subjective descriptive analysis.

Owner's pain scoring

The first five days after extraction of teeth the horse owners were asked to pain score their horses using two different scoring systems, the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS/Appendix 2.1) and the

Equine Pain Scale (EPS) (Appendix 2.2) (Breivik, et al., 2008) (Gleerup & Lindegaard, 2016). It was said that this was two separate scoring systems; the EPS should be scored using the handed out score chart and by using the VAS linear the worst pain imaginable could be compared with a colic horse throwing itself to the ground without any possibility of contact. The owners were instructed to evaluate the horses according to the signs described in the folder from Boehringer-Ingelheim about equine pain. The folder describes the facial expressions of a horse in acute pain and the horse's behaviour towards the surroundings (Appendix 2.3). The owners were told that the time of the day for the evaluation was not important.

Recordings and stills

From the video recordings a 30 sec. section was selected from the point when the horses stopped masticating. The section was shortened, if the horses were disturbed before the 30 sec. had past. These sections were used for evaluating of The Equine Pain Face (Appendix 3.1). From these sequences stills were selected at times 2 sec., 5sec., 10 sec., 15 sec. and 20 sec. If the pictures showed the horses in a position where HGS could be evaluated they were kept and used for evaluation using The Horse Grimace Scale (Appendix 3.2). The observers were be given the videos and stills divided in two equal groups with an unknown mixture of before and after sequences. To conduct these evaluations an expert in equine facial expressions and a trained equine veterinarian were chosen.

Statistical Analysis

Study 1

To compare the results from the questionnaire, the questions directly comparable were isolated and compared. These were the questions about eating behaviour, ability to eat grass, behaviour in the field and stable, changes during riding, social behaviour, head anxiety, and behaviour concerning the bit. The questions were translated in to quantitative values, and questions given negative answers were given the numerical value -1, neutral answers were given the numerical value 0 and positive answers were given the numerical value +1. This was performed by the use of Excel (Version 14.7.3(170325) ©2010 Microsoft Corporation). The questions relating to the time before extraction were summed up as were the questions related to the time after extraction. To test if the behavioural categories had changed, the results were compared using paired t-test in the statistical program Rstudio (Version 1.2.5033 - ©2009-2019 Rstudio, Inc.) The individual

behavioural parameters were investigated as well, to see if there were changes in these. Statistical difference was set for $p < 0,05$.

Study 2

The statistics of the questionnaires followed the same procedure as was applied to the questionnaire in study one, but the results were compared using paired Wilcoxon single-rank tests because of the smaller sample size. The individual behavioural parameters in this study are eating behaviour, behaviour in stable and field, herd behaviour, head anxiety and behaviour concerning the bit.

The average of the pain scoring done by the owners are calculated using Excel with a 95% confidence interval.

The EPS and HGS results used in the statistics are both the individual result and the combined results for the two observers.

The results from both HGS and EPF were tested using Wilcoxon single-ranked test because of the sample size. Because of the different numbers of usable pictures for the HGS, the average of the scores from the pictures were used to conduct the statistic. The inter-observer reliability was tested using a weighted Cohen's kappa and to test the association Kendall's tau-b is calculated. Both are calculated in Rstudio.

Results

Study 1

For study 1 a total of 47/126 questionnaires were answered.

The included horses have had between one and 14 ($8,6 \pm 4,2$) incisors and canine teeth extracted. The age of the included horses ranged from 11 to 27 years ($19,4 \pm 3,5$), 30 were geldings and 17 were mares. In the term of breed 24 Icelandic horses, 10 warmblood, 3 Norwegian fjord horses, 1 thoroughbred, 1 Haflinger, 1 sports pony, 2 Shetland ponies and 5 registered as mixtures were used.

Table 1: Summations of the horses included in the retrospective study

Number of horses	Number of extracted teeth	Age	Sex	Breed
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47	8,6 ± 4,2	19,4 ± 3,5	30 geldings 17 mares	24 Icelandic horses 10 warmblood 3 Norwegian fjord 2 Shetland ponies 1 Thoroughbred 1 Haflinger 1 Sportspony 5 mixtures
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The result of the retrospective study showed that the horses changed their behaviour after dental extraction. The results showed increased positivity from the owners with the mean score before of -0,13 and the mean after of 2,70. The mean difference is 2,83, 95% CI 2,03-3,63 ($p=6,27 \cdot 10^{-9}$).

Figure 3: Boxplot of the summation of the behavioural changes from the retrospective questionnaire from before and after surgery, showing that the horses' scores are more positive post extraction than prior to.

When testing the individual behavioural categories, a significant improvement was seen for eating behaviour ($p= 1,1 \cdot 10^{-6}$), behaviour in the field and/or stable ($p= 2,3 \cdot 10^{-7}$), changes during riding ($p= 2,8 \cdot 10^{-6}$), head anxiety ($p= 0,04$) and behaviour concerning the bit ($p= 0,009$). All of these changes were positive; meaning that in general, horses were more comfortable eating, behaved more normal in the field and stable, had less head anxiety and were more

positive towards the bit. No seen significant difference in social behaviour ($p= 0,09$) or the ability to eat grass ($p= 0,66$) was seen.

Running through the summations eight of 47 owners did not experience any differences in the general behaviour of their horses neither before nor after surgery. Of owners, that did experience differences, three of 39 did not notice the difference until after the extraction. Thirty-six of 39 had already discovered changes in behaviour. Only one owner showed an overall negative summation of scores (Appendix 4.1).

After dental extraction the owners described that the changes begins 14 days to 1 month after the extraction. The words used by the owners to describe the changes were “happier, more active, the horse is coming towards me, when it sees me, more eager towards food, less salivation/drooling, seems more at rest within itself and interact more in herd”. There have been a few negative comments mainly about prolonged eating time, less grooming activity and the high price of the extraction.

The words used to describe the owners’ emotions towards the operation are “good, fine, strange, concerned, nervous, bad, terrible”. Nineteen of the owners had positive or neutral feelings, 28 mainly used negative words to describe their feelings.

The question concerning the overall behavioural changes showed that there was no one who described the changes negatively, and most owners found that their horse was better or much better after extraction. The description of emotions prior to the surgery compared to the positivity in the overall changes post surgery, showed that owners change their feelings towards the extraction of teeth after obtaining their own experiences.

Figure 4: Distribution of the question concerning the overall behavioural changes evaluated by the owners. The figure shows that no owner reports the changes as negative, few owners are undecided, and most are positive. 1: Very bad 2: Bad 3: Un-changed 4: Better 5: Much better

44/47 of the owners would choose to have their horses' teeth extracted again, if they had another horse diagnosed with EOTRH. The remaining three replied, that it would depend on the horse. With regards to the question concerning other diseases, five owners answered PPID, four laminitis, one reduced vision, one diarrhoea, two orthopaedic problems and one allergic dermatitis/ summer eczema.

Study 2

The prospective study included 12 horses, aged between 16 and 25 years ($19,9 \pm 2,6$), five were mares and seven geldings. The breeds were seven Icelandic horses, two warmblood, two Norwegian fjord horses and one new forest.

Initially four additional horses were studied, but these horses showed no evidence of EOTRH on the radiological exam and were therefore excluded.

The number of teeth extracted was between one and twelve ($8,3 \pm 3,8$).

Table 2: Details of the 12 horses included in the prospective study.

Horse	Age	Breed	Sex	Removed teeth
Horse 1	19	Icelandic horse	Mare	101,102,103 201,202,203 301,302,303 401,402,403

Horse 2	24	Icelandic horse	Mare	101,102,103 201,202,203 301,302,303 401,402,403
Horse 3	25	Icelandic horse	Gelding	101,102,103 201,202,203 301,302,303 401,402,403
Horse 4	18	Icelandic horse	Mare	103 202,203 303 403
Horse 5	18	Icelandic horse	Mare	102 201,202 301,302 401,402
Horse 6	19	Icelandic horse	Gelding	102,103 202,203 301,302,303 401,402,403
Horse 7	20	New Forest	Gelding	103 203 302,303 403
Horse 8	16	Icelandic horse	Mare	301,302,303 401,402
Horse 9	18	Warmblood	Gelding	101,102,103 201,202,203 301,302,303 401,402,403
Horse 10	20	Norwegian fjord horse	Gelding	101,102,103 201,202,203 301,302,303 401,402,403
Horse 11	22	Norwegian fjord horse	Gelding	101,102,103 201,202,203 301,302,303 401,402
Horse 12	20	Warmblood	Gelding	103

Questionnaire

From the questionnaires there were significant differences in the comparison of the summations of answers from before surgery compared to after surgery with $p=0,0024$. Therefore we can reject the H_0 . Because of this, we state that the horses have changed behaviour when dealing with EOTRH.

Figure 5: Boxplot of the summations of behaviour from the prospective questionnaire from before and after, showing that the horses' scores are more positive post extraction than prior to extraction.

Looking through the answers from the owners it is found that the owners described their horse as more “happy, fresh, social and seeks more attention” after extraction of the affected teeth. They also mentioned that their horses were “more forward”, when ridden and were “more at rest within themselves” at the stable/ field. The significant differences and the descriptive words tell that the change were positive.

Testing the individual parameters, significant differences were found in eating behaviour ($p=0,005$), behaviour in the stable/field ($p=0,07$) and herd behaviour ($p=0,01$). No statistical differences were found in ability to eat grass ($p=1$), head anxiety ($p=1$) and behaviour concerning the bit ($p=0,09$).

To the question about the ability to bite off carrots seven owners noted, that their horse did so prior to extraction.

Half of the owners noted that they were fine about the procedure of extracting teeth, the other half were scared or find it transgressively, when asked before the extraction.

The overall behavioural change scored in the questionnaire had 5 ranks; 1: Very bad 2: Bad 3: un-changed 4: Better 5: Much better. None of the owners scored 1 or 2, one scored 3 and 11 scored 4 or 5.

Figure 6: Ranking of the question concerning the overall behavioural changes. The figure shows that not one owner reports the changes as negative, few owners are undecided, and most are positive. 1: Very bad 2: Bad 3: Un-changed 4: Better 5: Much better

The concurrent diseases of these horses were two PPID, one laminitis, one chronic dermal disease and one with chronic lameness and gastric ulcer.

Pain face evaluations

Of the video recordings 11 out of 12 cases could be used. One was excluded, because the horse kept finding small amounts of hay to eat, and therefore kept masticating, which made it impossible to evaluate.

When evaluating stills from the recordings at the selected time points, another horse was excluded since none of the images showed the horse in a position, where HGS could be analysed.

The expert observer found that nine out of 11 showed pain face before and two out of 11 after. One horse had pain face present at both times, one had no pain face present at either time and one had no prior to extraction but had present post extraction. There were statistical differences in the presents of pain face evaluated by the expert with $p = 0,02$ (Appendix 4.2).

The trained observer found 7 out of 11 horses showing pain face before and 3 out of 11 after. Two horses had pain face present at both times, three had no pain face present at either time and one had no prior to extraction but it was present post extraction. Statistical differences were not found in the evaluation of the trained observer ($p = 0,13$) (Appendix 4.2).

The inter rater reliability of EPF was 0,73 ($p = 0,0006$); 0,56 ($p = 0,039$) before surgery and 0,74 ($p = 0,01$) after surgery. The Equine Pain Face was present in 64% of the horses prior and 18 %

post surgery. The prevalences were found by selecting the horses, where both of the observers found pain face present. Testing results from both observers prior and post extraction with Wilcoxon single-ranked test showed significant differences with $p = 0,05$.

Table 3: Table of agreement of Equine Pain Face between the two observers before and after extraction of teeth affected by EOTRH

	Before	After
Agreed present pain face	7	2
Agreed no pain face	2	8
Disagreed	2	1

After evaluation of stills from videos of the 11 horses, one horse was excluded from the HGS, because none of the pictures had the head in the right posture for it to be evaluated. The expert chose to mark the categories she could not evaluate on the individual stills. The veterinarian gave those categories a zero, why it was chosen only to use horses with at least one complete scoring from both observers both prior and post surgery. These six horses were used for the statistics. The score using HGS was $3,2 \pm 2,4$ before and $1,6 \pm 1,7$ after for the expert and $2,4 \pm 2,0$ before and $1,2 \pm 1,2$ after for the trained observer (Appendix 4.2). The inter rater reliability of HGS was 0,77 ($p = 0,003$); 0,73 ($p = 0,04$) before surgery and 0,79 ($P = 0,04$) after surgery. Kendall's tau-b was 0,76; 0,75 prior and 0,79 post surgery.

The HGS calculations found that there were significant differences in the horses before and after the extraction with $2,8 \pm 2,2$ compared to $1,4 \pm 1,4$ ($p = 0,03$). There were not significant differences, when looking at the individual observers; expert $p = 0,1$, veterinarian $p = 0,2$.

Owner pain score

Comparison of the owners' pain evaluation during the first five post operative days showed that most of the owners found their horses to have decreasing pain behaviour over this five days observational period. Moreover, most owners only found their horses displaying few behavioural signs of pain behaviour. Only three of the owners managed to use the EPS, eight of them assigned scores that were not used in that category. Eleven owners managed to use the VAS and one did not return her score charts. The three usable scores on EPS went from 4-0 on the first day to 5-0 on the last day. The VAS score decreased from 7-0 ($2,8 \pm 2,4$) the first day to 4-0 ($1,5 \pm 1,5$) on the last day. Testing the results from day one to the results from day five showed no significant difference, $p = 0,06$.

Figure 7: A boxplot of the VAS score given by the owners, showing that the horses are evaluated as having a small decrease in the amount of pain during the five days. The horses are still evaluated as having some pain on the last day of scoring.

Observations

During the first visit all of the horses were observant/attentive towards people with whom they were unfamiliar, but six of them did not show any signs of interaction/contact towards the person. The horses were mainly standing nearby the others horses, when seen in the field.

Four of the horses were drooling prior to getting a carrot and five of the horses were spontaneously licking their lips, when they were observed in an undisturbed manner.

When observing the horses biting off a carrot, the horses attempted to achieve the carrot in many ways. The carrot was broken by the incisors in either the upper or lower part of the mouth, bitten in small pieces until the diameter decreased, moved towards the un- or lesser-affected teeth or the horse tried to pull the entire carrot in to the mouth. Only two of the 12 horses bit off the carrot without hesitation.

At the follow up examination approximately 50% of the horses had small alveolar sequestra, which were removed. Eight of the owners report that the horses were now happier, more active and one mentions that her horse's eyes seemed bigger. Two owners noticed that their horses

were in pain the first few days after extraction and two responded that their impressions were that the horses experienced less pain than expected.

At the last visit between six and eight weeks after surgery, the six horses which did not choose to interact at the first visit now freely wanted to interact to the person, whom they were unfamiliar to. The horses in general seemed happier and only one of them was still spontaneously licking its lips. None of them were drooling prior to the carrot test. Of the horses that were still able to bite off over a carrot, one was still not willing to do so.

Discussion

The differences in behaviour shown in these studies are expected, because of the anecdotes of the behaviour after the operation. The numerical values of the statistics should be read with some restraint. The scores are formed from a simple thought of using the numbers -1, 0 and 1 to describe the answers. It is not taken in to consideration that some owners report differences before extraction, some after extraction and some at both times. One could discuss if the answers should have been weighted, but it is chosen not to do so. This does not change the fact that there are significant differences.

When analysing the individual behavioural categories, significant differences in both studies are found in the horses' eating behaviour and their behaviour in the stable and field. In the retrospective study there are questions concerning the behaviour when ridden, showing significant differences. This behavioural category is not included in the prospective study. One could argue that it should have been, but it is excluded because of the relative short duration of the study. The possibility that the owners had not started riding or that the horse would not have had time to adjust to the new circumstances would mean too few answers or the answers would be too biased.

Social behaviour is also only included in the retrospective study. This could have been included in the prospective as well. The retrospective study showed no difference in the social behaviour. It may be because the horses' social behaviour are not affected, but this can also be because the owners are not observant to the social behaviour of horses on a daily basis. Many owners never observe their horses in the field with other horses.

There are no differences in the ability to eat grass. Only one owner reported that she thinks her horse is troubled. Her horse is able to eat grass, but it often gets rots along with it. When listening to the anecdotes, owners are often concerned about the horse's ability to eat grass. Here

is it shown that horses are able to eat grass both prior and post extraction. The answers from the questionnaires show that horses need a bit longer grass, but they learn to eat it again after just a few days.

The behavioural categories “ head anxiety” and “behaviour concerning the bit” only show significant differences in the retrospective study. This may be caused by the small sample size in the prospective. When looking at the p-value for these categories, it is clear that these values are quite close to the cut off value compared to the others. Therefore, it may just be a coincidence that the categories have fallen out on each side of the cut off. If one should decide on a result being better than another, the retrospective result would be chosen because of the sample size. The categories with differences are all categories, in which the owner is more involved or interacts more with the horse, why this may be the categories one would expect owners to be more aware of the changes.

As mentioned above the owners describe the positive changes after the extraction starting between seven days and one month after surgery. This matches the seen healing process. At the time of the follow up examination in the prospective study, the extraction sockets are filled with granulation tissue and the gingiva is nearly intact. As long as the horse is healing, one must assume that changed behaviour will occur. Once the healing is complete the horse has also had time adapted to the sensations in its mouth and the pain has gone, why the behaviour returns to the behaviour prior to the disease.

The positive words used to describe the changes by the owners are all terms of behaviour concerning the horse; the negative words are mainly describing changes, which have an impact on the owner. A prolonged eating time is not necessarily negative in the mind of the horse and the negativity concerning the cost of the operation could perhaps be managed with alignment of expectations between the owner and the veterinarian.

There are a high number of owners (59,6% retrospective, 50% prospective), who report concerns or feel scared about the operation. This may be handled with better information to the horse owners, why it is important to increase knowledge for the veterinarians.

Only three of the owners do not report changes before the extraction in the retrospective study. This may be biased by the fact that the study is retrospective, why thinking back on the time before can make them see the changes. It is believed that several of the owners would not have been aware of the changes, if they were asked prior to the extraction, because of the slow changes, caused by the slow development of the disease. In the prospective study only one does not report changes prior to extraction. It was expected that more owners would not have reported

changes prior to extraction, but this could be biased by the questions, as they made the owners look for changes that they might not have thought of earlier.

None of the answers to the overall changes of the horse were negative, but one of the comparisons in the retrospective study of the summation scores is negative. This shows that there is a bias between the written comments compared to the overall view. The reason behind this bias may be that humans find greater impact to negative experiences than to positive experiences. The psychological effect of the negative experiences outweighs the effect of good experiences (Baumeister, Bratslavsky, Finkenauer, & Vohs, 2001).

Furthermore, there is a selection bias in this study. All of the owners have chosen to have teeth extracted, why one must assume that they have done so, because they hope for an increase of the welfare for their horse. Therefore, these owners may subconsciously be looking for positive changes.

To validate the conducted summation, the overall summations are compared to the owners overall satisfaction with their horses' behavioural changes. Nine cases with no changes in the summation are found, and nine owners report their horses as unchanged in terms of behaviour; five of these cases overlap. The last four cases with summations showing no changes report positive satisfaction with scores 4 (three of them) or 5 (one of them). The last four owners scoring 3 are summarised 1 (three of them) and -2(one of them). Therefore, the summation seems to be useful to perform a quantitative test of the questionnaires.

The two scales HGS and EQUUS-FAP have already been used to describe dental and head pain, which is why facial expressions may also be useful in evaluating pain before and after extraction of teeth diagnosed with EOTRH (Coneglian, Borges, Weber, Bertagnon, & Michelotto, 2020) (van Loon & Van Dierendonck, 2017). In this study it was decided to use the HGS, because this is the only one, which has previously been used to describe dental pain previously, and it is directly comparable to EPF since these two only include facial expressions.

The Equine Pain Face is either present with the horses or not. Both observers had fewer horses with pain face present after surgery and there were significant differences, when comparing the results of both observers before and after surgery. The expert had significant differences based solitarily on her own results; the veterinarian did not have significant differences. The kappa for all the observations of EPF is 0,72, which shows a substantial level of agreement. The kappa value of 0,56 prior to surgery shows a moderate level of agreement (0,41-0,60), and the value of

0,74 post surgery shows a substantial level of agreement. When evaluating these kappa values it seems that there are greater level of agreement, when deciding that pain face is not present than deciding if it is present (Landis & Koch, 1977). The expressions may differ in clarity, because of the lighting, long fur, placement of the head collar and mane or forelock, making it hard to see even small changes.

The Horse Grimace Scale is a quantitative scale based on stills. For this study, it is chosen to select stills at five time points from the recordings used for EPF. Some of the horses in the recordings are moving quite a lot, they are turning their head away, kicking with the front legs and listening to sounds from the surroundings. All of these disturbances will make it more difficult to evaluate the stills. After the evaluations of the observers one could argue, that it would have been better to use more stills, as only six of the cases could be included.

The results of the HGS show a significant difference from before surgery to after surgery. Since this is based on a sample size just big enough to perform the test, some uncertainty will exist, especially because there are no significant differences found when looking at the individual observers. The inter rater reliability is higher using this scoring system, compared to the EFP, especially when evaluating the horses prior to surgery. The fact that the observer has a picture to compare with a picture of the individual categories makes it perhaps easier to score, than if the observer watches a recording, where differences between facial expressions of pain and facial expressions of horses performing all sorts of behaviour need to be distinguished. The fact that HGS includes only six of ten horses, most of them with only one scoring from five pictures, show that in this field study it is a more difficult tool to use compared to EPF, with which all 11 of 11 horses are included.

As mentioned above the two types of pain face evaluations have been developed in hospital settings, why there is some uncertainty, if they are useful in the horses' everyday habitat. In a field trial there will be many unknown and uncontrollable disturbances and therefore the selection of recording sections and stills cannot be as strict and precise as it may be in a hospital settings. The time chosen for the recording is 30 sec because one cannot be sure that the horse has its head in the right lateral view at a shorter time-frame. For the stills five different times slots have been chosen with the shortest interval in the beginning of the recording because it is assumed that the horses might show the clearest pain face immediately after being exposed to the possible pain. A possible bias, in using video recordings as done in this study, is the possibility that the observers are able to recognise some of the horses and thereby see the changes in the coat or the season caused by the relative long duration of the study. This will make the observer able to

differ between the two times. The fact that the observers are given the recordings in two groups, will decrease the potential bias.

The horses in the recordings have more or less behaviour towards the observer or the owner. It is difficult to make a set-up in a field trial, where humans are at a distance so the horse does not acknowledge them, but the humans are still in a distance where the details in the recordings are sufficient.

It is believed that EPF will be a good and simple tool to evaluate dental pain in horses. The scoring of HGS shows a mean score of $2,8 \pm 2,2$, which shows that the horses are only showing a mild to moderate pain in this study, even though the pain is believed to be more severe. One must always keep in mind that pain is a mixture of the nociception and emotion. The knowledge of nociception is described, but no-one will ever be able to look inside the horses' minds to compare emotions. The pain followed by EOTRH is believed to be chronic because of the time frame of the disease, and therefore some adaptation to the pain must be considered, why the pain may seem to be less severe than expected (Zautra, Hamilton, & Burke, 1999). Since the EPF is a qualitative scale, it only tells us whether or not the horse is in pain. However, this will be sufficient to evaluate whether or not to treat the horse.

This study shows that it is possible to evaluate dental pain using facial expressions, why it is important for veterinarians to have knowledge about these. To treat the horses in the best possible way we must make sure that their welfare is excellent. In the Danish Animal Welfare Legislation it is written that animals should be protected in the best way possible against pain, suffering, permanent disability and significant disadvantages (Miljø- og Fødevarestyrelsen, 2020). Using the facial expressions of horses we are provided with a quick and easy tool to tell us if we need to find a possible explanation to why the horses show these signs.

A study of facial expressions showing emotional stress in horses is conducted. This study finds resemblances between the facial expressions of pain and the facial expressions of emotional stress. The similar characteristics are dilated nostrils and raised inner brow, why further studies should look into the separation of these, but it may never fully be differentiated because of the connection between pain and stress (Lundblad, Rashid, Rhodin, & Andersen, 2020).

The owner evaluation of his or her horse is not without problems either. Most of the owners did not manage to use the EPS, even though they were told to score according to the handed-out score chart. The main problem was, that they were scoring digits, which are not present under the specific category. It is believed that the owners have used the chart, but the fact that scoring is

not numerical continuously causes the mistakes, and therefore an elaborate description and possibly training is necessary, if the EPS is to be used.

The VAS scale is a much easier tool for the owners to use. This tool only shows one digit at the linear, why the rate of mistakes is the smallest possible. The problem with the scores on the VAS linear is that the observer influences it. The appearance of the horse's mouth and the odour from the healing site could potentially influence the owners to score the horses higher, than if the operation area was not so obvious. One might suspect, that the concerns regarding the future welfare of the horses or the consequences of the operation would also affect the score.

The observation that the horses seem to be interacting more with people, both their owners and foreign people, after having their teeth extracted, can be seen as a sign of decreased or absence of pain in the horses (McLennan, et al., 2019). Six of the 12 horses in the study did not interact at the first visit, but all of them freely interacted at the last visit after 6-8 weeks.

In a study by Pritchett et al. from 2007 a numerical rating scale of behaviours are used to score pain in horses after exploratory celiotomy. One of the behaviour categories is "Response to approach". Here the horses are graded according to level of interaction: the horse that interacts with the observer has the lowest score and the horse that does not move and takes the ears back, has the highest score. The lowest score is the horse in the least pain. The six horses participating in this study would get the score 2; they look at the observer with the ears forward (Pritchett, Ulibarri, Roberts, Schneider, & Sellon, 2003). There could be many reasons, why these horses did not interact on during the first observations, but the horses all change their behaviour so evidently during the second observation, that it must be assumed that the extraction of teeth is the cause behind that change of behaviour. The rest of the horses interacted at all visits. The fact that the rest of the horses are still seeking contact is not a sign that the horses are not in pain, but only shows that they have not changed their specific behaviour.

Pain behaviour differs between horses. This is partly because of the emotional factor regarding pain, but we must also take in to consideration that we do not know the full pathogenesis of the disease, why it is not established if the pain differs in the different stages of the disease. When evaluating the horses included in the study, it is believed that there is quite a big difference in the pain observed in the horses.

Comparison of the ability to bite off carrots also shows a difference in the horses' behaviour. The owners note that seven of the 12 horses are able to do so before having their teeth extracted. At the first visit only two of the 12 horses bite off the carrot. It is also seen that the horses find several ways to get the carrot. This may be the reason why the owners have the experience that

the carrots are bitten off. Asking the owners to perform a carrot test themselves, may give the wrong impression of the ability. Therefore, in order to achieve a more precise indication of the pain in the incisors, it is believed that the carrot tests should be performed by the veterinarian, recorded for evaluation or at least be described in details to achieve the right knowledge.

Seven of the 12 horses in the study drooled, licked or did both prior to the carrot test. This behaviour was noted once in the reviewed articles in relation to fractured teeth (Earley & Rawlinson, 2013). Hypersalivation is described as a symptom of FORL in cats (Myhre & Ueland, 2009). This feature should be part of an evaluation concerning dental pain. Only one of the horses still lick spontaneously at the last visit and the rest of the horses have much less or completely stopped drooling. This may indicate that the disease in the mouth is better because the production of saliva decreased, indicating that it is not needed to the same extent.

Furthermore, horses suffering from EOTRH may also have periodontitis, which saliva will help reduce (Klugh, 2004). There are multiple causes why horses lick or drool, and the horses could suffer from something else, which might cause them to do so. This means that it could be due to other circumstances that all these horses change behaviour. However, it would be strange if all of these horses changed behaviour due to something else at this exact time.

Half of the horses in this study had alveolar sequestra at the follow up examination. The veterinarians did a thorough debridement of the vacated alveoli but it did not seem to be sufficient to avoid the formation of sequestra. Therefore it is recommended that all horses should have a follow up examination, even though the performing veterinarian believes that there will be no complications.

In this study none of the horses were treated with antibiotics post extraction. There were no reported complications post extraction, except the formation for sequestra. Therefore, it is suggested that veterinarians should not prescribe antibiotics as a standard for this procedure.

The representation of Icelandic horses in this study is high compared to the reported breeds from other studies (Sykora, Pieber, Simhofer, Hackl, Brodesser, & Brandt, 2014) (Pearson, Mansfield, Conaway, & Koput, 2013) (Hole & Staszuk, 2018). It is not reported in any of the reviewed studies that there might be a higher prevalence of Icelandic horses with this disease. This may indicate that there is a genetic factor in the aetiology. However, it could also be a bias, because of the population of breeds in Denmark or just the patient base at the clinic, compared to the populations used in the other publications. The combination of the patient base of the clinic, compared to other clinics, is unknown. SEGES estimate that there are approximately 25%

Icelandic horses in Denmark (email correspondence) compared to the 51% in this study, why the Icelandic horse is still overrepresented in this study. Another reason behind this could be a higher life expectancy of the Icelandic horses, as the disease is often seen in geriatric horses, or the possibility that it is just a coincidence that most of the cases are of that breed.

It has been proposed that PPID predispose for EOTRH, why one could think that the prevalence of PPID among horses diagnosed with EOTRH would be higher than among the general population. In the retrospective study five of 47 owners report PPID as concurrent disease, which gives a prevalence of 10,6%. A Danish study of 33 horses above 15 years finds a prevalence of 21% (95% confidence interval is 10% - 39%) (Christiansen, 2009). A comparison between the prevalence from the reviewed study to the conducted study shows that the prevalence is within the 95% confidence interval. This study prevalence could be underestimated, because this prevalence is based on the owner reports and not based on diagnostic testing of all the horses.

Conclusion

This study showed a positive significant change in behaviour post extraction of teeth affected by EOTRH. It is found that the horses show signs of pain, when diagnosed with EOTRH, and that the signs decrease after extraction. In both the retrospective study and the prospective study the significant changes were found in eating behaviour and behaviour in the stable/field. Owners mainly describe the changes with words like “happier, more forward and more at rest within itself”. The change in response to approach was positive.

There were no significant changes in the horses’ ability to eat grass. The owners described that the horses were eating grass a few days after extraction, and that they were impressed by the quick adaption to the circumstances.

Facial expressions can be a tool used for dental pain. In this study the horses were asked to bite off a carrot to display the signs of acute tooth pain within a chronic disease. The use of facial expressions demands training, and it is believed that most horses in pain will be discovered using the Equine Pain Face compared to the Horse Grimace Scale. However, the owners’ use of pain scales did not seem to give accurate results.

Knowledge of the disease is still not sufficient, why awareness about the disease and the possibilities should be increased. The thought that a carrot test could help the owners awareness

to a problem, does not seem to work. The owners need to know how to perform the test right if this should work.

Many owners felt uncomfortable about the tooth extraction procedure and may therefore choose to leave the teeth as they are or to euthanize the horse.

EOTRH should be acknowledged as a painful disease and veterinarians should be aware of this disease, if the owners report unspecific decrease in welfare in geriatric horses.

Perspectives

The prevalence of EOTRH is suggested to be between 62,0% and 93,7% for horses above 10 years, and it seems that the prevalence might be rising with age (Rehrl, Schröder, Müller, Staszuk, & Lischer, 2018). This study shows that pain is associated with the disease, and that the horses increase their welfare post extraction. These statements should lead to further investigative studies to increase knowledge about the disease.

This study leads to a recommendation of future studies concerning the prevalence of the disease in Icelandic horses, the prevalence of horses with concurrent chronic or systemic diseases, who develop EOTRH, pain in relation to the different stages of the disease as well as the use of antibiotics post extraction. Future studies should focus on how to validate the different pain scoring scales in the horses' natural habitats, and not least, how to recognise chronic pain in horses.

Conflicts of interest

Metacam® for treatment of pain post extraction is sponsored by Boehringer-Ingelheim, who has no inappropriately influence on the study.

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Appendix 1.1

Retrospective questionnaire

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Tak fordi du vil deltage i dette vigtige projekt om EOTRH, som skal hjælpe med at fremme velfærden blandt heste med denne og andre tandsygdomme. Spørgsmålene må meget gerne udbygges, hvor det er muligt. På forhånd tak.

Generel information:

Ejers navn:

Hestens navn:

Hestens køn:

Hestens race:

Hestens brug:

Hestens konkurrenceniveau (hvis relevant):

Hvor gammel var hesten, da den fik konstateret EOTRH:

Hvor lang tid gik der før den blev opereret:

Hvornår blev den opereret (dato/måned/år):

Hvilke tænder fik den fjernet:

De første spørgsmål drejer sig om tiden inden hesten fik fjernet sine tænder. Det er ikke sikkert, at du husker alt, men svar gerne med så mange detaljer som du kan huske.

101. Hvornår opdagede du at hesten havde problemer med fortænderne?

102. Hvordan opdagede du at hesten havde problemer med fortænderne?

103. Observerede du ændringer i hestens æde-adfærd?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

104. Hvad fodrede du hesten med (stråfodertype, kraftfodertype, vitaminer/mineraler)?

105. Ville/kunne hesten æde gulerødder, æbler og godbidder?

106. Ville/kunne hesten bide gulerødder og æbler over med fortænderne?

107. Ville/kunne hesten græsse?

108. Var der forskel på om det var kort eller langt græs?
Hvis ja, Hvad foretrak den?

109. Bemærkede du ændret adfærd hos din hest på stald eller fold?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

110. Observerede du ændringer i hestens adfærd overfor andre heste?
Hvis ja, hvilke?

111. Udførte din hest socialadfærd i form af leg eller soignering af foldkammerater?

112. Oplevede du, at hesten var "hovedsky" eller på nogen måde reagerede i forbindelse med strigling, håndtering i/omkring hovedet ved pålægning af grime eller lignende?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

113. Ville hesten gerne have bid i munden, eller vægrede den sig på nogen måde?
Hvis ja, hvornår/hvordan?

114. Red du din hest uden bid? Var der forskel mellem at ride hesten med og uden bid?

115. Var der ændet opførsel hos din hest under ridning?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

116. Havde hesten normal hovedholdning under ridning, eller var der ændringer af dette?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

117. Havde hesten haft perioder med dårlig mave?

118. Fejlede hesten andre ting sideløbende med EOTRH?
Hvis ja, hvilke?

119. Blev den behandlet med medicin mod denne/disse lidelser?

120. Hvordan havde du det med at hesten skulle have fjernet tænder?

De næste spørgsmål handler om om tiden efter operationen.

121. Fik hesten medicin efter operationen? Kan du huske hvilken type?

122. Havde hesten nogen komplikationer/problemer i forbindelse med, eller umiddelbart efter operationen (manglende opheling, smerter, sekvestre)?

123. Observerede du adfærdsændringer hos din hest i stalden efter tandoperationen?
Hvis ja, hvordan vil du beskrive disse ændringer? Og hvornår skete ændringerne? (umiddelbart efter operation, dage efter, uger efter, måneder efter?)

124. Observerede du adfærdsændringer hos din hest på folden efter tandoperationen?
Hvis ja, hvordan vil du beskrive disse ændringer? Og hvornår skete ændringerne? (umiddelbart efter operation, dage efter, uger efter, måneder efter?)

125. Udførte din hest socialadfærd i form af leg eller soignering af foldkammerater efter operationen? Var der forskel fra før operationen?

126. Var din hest "hovedsky" efter behandlingen?
Hvis ja, var det anderledes end tidligere?

127. Hang tungen ud af munden på hesten efter operationen?

4

Hvis ja, i hvilke situationer?

128. Ændrede du hestens foder efter operationen?
Hvis ja, hvad og/eller hvordan?

129. Åd hesten anderledes end før operationen?

130. Var hesten mere eller mindre interesseret i godbidder end før operationen?

131. Ville/kunne hesten græsse?
Hvis ja, kunne den finde ud af det?

132. Observerede du adfærdsændringer under ridning hos hesten efter tandoperationen?
Hvis ja, hvordan vil du beskrive disse ændringer? Og hvornår skete ændringerne? (umiddelbart efter operation, dage efter, uger efter, måneder efter?)

133. Ændrede du dit bid efter operationen?
Hvis ja, fra hvad til hvad?

134. Ændrede hesten adfærd i forbindelse med pålægning af trense og bid?

135. Ændrede du noget ved din ridning?
Hvis ja, hvad ændrede du?

136. Hvordan ville du beskrive, at hesten havde det efter i forhold til før operationen?

Meget dårlig	Dårlig	Uændret	Bedre	Meget bedre

137. Ville du vælge at få fjernet fortænder på en hest en anden gang, hvis hesten fik stillet diagnosen EOTRH?

138. Lever hesten endnu?

Hvis nej, hvad døde den af og hvor længe efter operationen?

Hvis ja, hvor lang tid er det siden, hesten blev opereret?

Appendix 1.2

Prospective questionnaire prior to extraction

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Tak fordi du vil deltage i dette vigtige projekt om EOTRH, som skal hjælpe med at fremme velfærden blandt heste med denne og andre tandsygdomme. Spørgsmålene må meget gerne uddybes, hvor det er muligt. På forhånd tak.

Generel information:

Ejers navn:

Hestens navn:

Hvor gammel er hesten:

Hestens køn:

Hestens race:

Hestens brug:

Hestens konkurrenceniveau (hvis relevant):

1. Hvornår opdagede du at hesten havde problemer med fortænderne?

2. Hvordan opdagede du at hesten havde problemer med fortænderne?

Før behandling – alle spørgsmålene i denne sektion gælder hestens adfærd INDEN fjernelse af tænderne med EOTRH

3. Observerer du ændringer i hestens æde-adfærd?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

4. Hvad fodrer du hesten med (stråfodertype, kraftfodertype, vitaminer/mineraler)?

5. Vil/kan hesten spise gulerødder, æbler og godbidder?

6. Vil/kan hesten bide gulerødder og æbler over med fortænderne?

7. Vil/kan hesten gerne græsse?

8. Er der forskel på om det er kort eller langt græs?
Hvis ja, hvad foretrækker den?

9. Har du bemærket ændret adfærd hos din hest?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

10. Har du bemærket ændringer i hestens adfærd i flokken?
Hvis ja, hvilke?

11. Har du oplevet at hesten har været "hovedsky" eller på nogen måde reageret i forbindelse med strigling, håndtering i/omkring hovedet/pålægning af grime eller lignende?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

12. Vil hesten gerne have bid i munden, eller vægrer den sig på nogen måde?
Hvis ja, hvornår/hvordan?

13. Rider du den nogensinde uden bid? Er der forskel mellem at ride hesten med og uden bid?

14. Har hesten ændret sin hovedholdning under ridning?
Hvis ja, hvordan?

15. Har hesten haft perioder med dårlig mave?

16. Hvordan har du det med at hesten skal have opereret sine fortænder ud?

17. Fejler hesten andet udover EOTRH?
Hvis ja, hvilke?

Appendix 1.3

Prospective questionnaire post extraction

KØBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET
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Igen tak fordi du vil deltage i dette vigtige projekt om EOTRH, som skal hjælpe med at fremme velfærden blandt heste med denne og andre tandsygdomme. Spørgsmålene må meget gerne uddybes, hvor det er muligt. På forhånd tak.

Generel information:

Ejers navn:

Hestens navn:

Efter behandling – alle spørgsmålene i denne sektion gælder hestens adfærd minimum 6 uger efter fjernelse af tænderne med EOTRH

18. Var hesten i nogen form for behandling før tænderne bliver fjernet?

19. Fik hesten fjernet alle fortænder eller kun enkelte?
Hvis enkelte kan du huske hvilke den fik fjernet?

20. Fik den anden medicin end det smertestillende?
Hvis ja, hvad fik den?

21. Har du observeret adfærdændringer på stald hos hesten efter tandoperationen?
Hvis ja, hvordan vil du beskrive disse ændringer? Og hvornår skete ændringerne? (umiddelbart efter operation, dage efter, uger efter, måneder efter?)

22. Har du observeret adfærdændringer på fold hos hesten efter tandoperationen?
Hvis ja, hvordan vil du beskrive disse ændringer? Og hvornår skete ændringerne? (umiddelbart efter operation, dage efter, uger efter, måneder efter?)

23. Udfører din hest socialadfærd i form af leg eller soignering af foldkammerater?
Gjorde den det før operationen?

1

24. Har hesten været "hovedsky" efter behandlingen?
Hvis ja, er det anderledes end før?

25. Hænger tungen ud af munden på hesten?
Hvis ja, i hvilke situationer?

26. Har du ændret hestens foder?
Hvis ja, hvad og/ eller hvordan?

27. Æder hesten anderledes end før behandling?

28. Vil hesten have godbidder i form af gulerødder / æbler / andet?

29. Vil /kan hesten gerne græsse?
Hvis ja, kan den finde ud af det?

30. Har du observeret adfærdsændringer under ridning hos hesten efter tandoperationen?
Hvis ja, hvordan vil du beskrive disse ændringer? Og hvornår skete ændringerne? (umiddelbart efter operation, dage efter, uger efter, måneder efter?)

31. Har du ændret dit bid?
Hvis ja, fra hvad til hvad?

32. Har hesten ændret adfærd i forbindelse med pålægning af trense og bid?

33. Har du ændret noget ved din ridning?
Hvis ja, hvad har du ændret?

34. Hvordan vil du beskrive, at hesten har det nu i forhold til før operationen?

Meget dårlig	Dårlig	Uændret	Bedre	Meget bedre

35. Ville du vælge at få fjernet fortænder på en hest en anden gang, hvis hesten fik stillet diagnosen EOTRH?

Appendix 2.1

Visual analogue scale (VAS)

The VAS is a 10 cm line where one end shows no pain and the opposite shows worst imaginable pain. The observer is then to put a mark in between to score the pain. The scale is influenced by the time spend at the horse and the emotional status of the observer (de Grauw & van Loon, 2016) (Breivik, et al., 2008)

Appendix 2.2

Equine Pain Scale

(Gleerup & Lindegaard, 2016)

The Equine Pain Scale

For the specific definitions of each grade of each of the categories please refer to the "Equine pain scale".

To obtain a pain score of any given horse, start observing the horse from a distance to score the first 7 categories of the Equine Pain Scale then approach the horse in the box stall, open the door and evaluate the horse's response to this followed by the horse's response to the approaching observer. Finally, offer the horse some hay or other feed that it would normally eat and observe the horse's response to this. After scoring all 9 categories, sum up the result to yield a final pain score for the specific time point.

Interpretation of the result: Any horse scoring 4 at any parameter and/or having a total pain score of 8-10 or above should be considered in pain and thereby in need for further diagnostic work up, immobilization and/or additional analgesic treatment.

Behaviour category	Patient name:			Patient J.no.:		
	Time:	Time:	Time:	Time:	Time:	Time:
Pain face						
Gross pain behaviour*						
Activity						
Location in the stall						
Posture/ weight bearing						
Head position						
Attention towards the painful area						
Interactive behaviour						
Response to food						
SUM						

*Gross pain behaviour includes all readily visible behaviours like: excessive head movements (vert/hor), flinches, kicking, pawing, rolling, tail swishing, mouth playing, repeated stretching etc.

The Equine Pain Scale

Behaviour category	Score				
	0	1	2	3	4
Pain face	No pain face		Pain face present	Intense pain face	
Gross pain behaviour*	None		Occasional		Continuous
Activity	Exploring, attention towards surroundings or resting	No movement		Restless	Depressed
Location in the stall	At the door watching the environment	Standing in the middle, facing the door	Standing in the middle facing the sides	Standing in the middle facing back or standing in the back	
Posture/weight bearing	Normal posture and normal weight bearing	Foot intermittent of the ground/occasional weight shift	Pinched (groove between abd. muscles visible)	Continuously taking foot off the ground and trying to replace it.	No weight bearing. Abnormal weight distribution
Head position	Foraging, below withers or high	Level of withers	Below withers		
Attention towards the painful area	Does not pay attention to painful area		Brief attention to painful area (e.g. flank watching)		Biting, nudging or looking at painful area (e.g. flank watching)
Interactive behaviour	Looks at observer or moves to observer when approached	Looks at observer does not move	Does not look at observer or moves away avoids contact	Does not move, not reacting/introverted	
Response to food	Takes food with no hesitation	Looks at food		No response to food	

*Gross pain behaviour includes all readily visible behaviours like, excessive head movements (vert/horiz), flehmen, kicking, pawing, rolling, tail swishing, mouth playing, repeated stretching etc.

The Equine Pain Face

Evaluating the facial expression of the horse should be done while the horse is undisturbed. Look at the horse systematically, start with the ears, then the eyes, the lower head and finally evaluate the facial expression as a whole; in most cases more than one feature of the pain face is present when a horse is in pain.

Appendix 2.3

ET ER MIDDAG	FORMIDDAG	VAS AFLÆSNING: DATO
		1
		2
		3
		4
		5
		6
		7

DATO:
 DRYLIGE:
 HESTENS NAVN:
 DIAGNOSE:

SMERTEVURDERINGS SKEMA

SÅDAN BRUGES VAS LINEALEN

SMERTEVURDERING
 For at følge udviklingen af din hests smertevoldende sygdom kan du anvende denne VAS lineal. (VAS står for visuel analog skala).
 Det er vigtigt det er den samme person og en person, som kender hesten, som vurderer den hver gang.

SÅDAN GØR DU:
 1 Kik på hesten og vurder om den har "Ingen smerte" eller "Væst tænkelige smerte." Stil markøren der hvor hestens smerte er på det givne tidspunkt. **OBS:** Det er den umiddelbare opfattelse af hestens smerteytringer der skal ligge til grund for VAS-scoren.

2 Vend linealen og aflæs værdien. Skriv den i smertevurderings skemaet til venstre så kan du bedre følge op på hestens smerteudvikling.

Boehringer Ingelheim Vetmedica
 2100 Kbh Ø - Tlf. 39 15 88 88
 www.bivet.nu/dk

Vurder smerteudvikling hos hesten med:

VAS LINEAL VISUEL ANALOG SKALA

DK-4182-17-01-6

SÅDAN VISER DIN HEST SMERTE

Heste kan ikke på samme måde som mennesker give udtryk for smerte. Derfor går alt for mange heste rundt og har ondt – uden at komme i behandling eller få den ro, de har brug for. Det kan nemt føre til længerevarende skadeforløb eller sygdomme, fordi problemet bliver håndteret for sent.

Ny forskning har dog vist, at hesten rent faktisk har et "pain face", altså et ansigtsudtryk der tydeligt signalerer smerte. Man skal bare lære disse tegn at kende og øve sig i at tyde dem.

HESTENS PAIN FACE
 Når en hest har smerter, viser den som regel flere af nedenstående tegn. Jo mere markante tegn desto mere intense smerter.

LÆR DE FEM TEGN AT KENDE

- "LAVE" ØRER**
 Afstanden mellem ørerne bliver større og åbningen i ørerne vender ofte ud til siderne. Ørerne er ikke opmærksomme med et øre fremme eller bagud og det andet der lytter til omgivelserne.
- TREKANT OVER ØJE**
 Musklerne omkring øjnene er spændt og øjet får et karakteristisk "trekantet" udseende. Blikket bliver anspændt og indadvendt.
- UDVIDEDE NÆSEBOR**
 Næseborene ser mere firkantede ud i forhold til den normale aflange, bløde form. Dette ses tydeligt, når hesten trækker vejret ind.
- SPÆNDT ANSIGTSMUSKULATUR**
 Musklerne på siden af hestens ansigt bliver mere spændte og ses derfor tydeligere.
- KANTET MULE**
 Læberne ser spændte ud og mulen får en mere kantet form i forhold til den runde mule hos heste uden smerter.

LÆS MERE OM PAIN FACE PÅ
LangtHesteLiv.dk

ANDRE TEGN PÅ SMERTE

Pain Face er en enkel og hurtig metode til at vurdere, om din hest har smerte. Men for at danne dig et mere fyldstgørende billede, bør du også kigge på hestens adfærd. F.eks.:

PLACERING I BOKSEN
 En smertefri hest vil ofte stå forrest i boksen, mens en hest med smerter gerne står midt i eller bagest i boksen og måske kigger væk.

HOVEDHOLDNING
 Heste holder normalt hovedet højt, med mindre de spiser. Smertepåvirkede heste vil holde hovedet på eller under niveau med lansemærket.

OPMÆRKSOMHED
 En smertefri hest vil kigge på og bevæge sig mod dig når du kommer. Ved smerter vil den oftest kun kigge uden at bevæge sig eller evt. blive helt indelukket.

FØDE
 En hest vil normalt tage foder til sig uden at tøve. Er den smertepåvirket, vil den ofte nøjes med at kigge på foderet eller evt. ignorere det.

Appendix 3.1

The Equine Pain Face

Descriptions of facial expressions according to The Equine Pain Face (Gleerup, Forkman, Lindegaard, & Andersen, 2015).

Pain face feature	Detailed description
Asymmetrical/low ears	Both ears are moving in different directions or are placed in asymmetrical positions with neither of the ears facing directly forward or back. There may be lowering of both ears (increased distance between them) with the opening of the ears facing the sides or slightly back. The ears may be both asymmetrical and low.
Angled eye	There is tension of the <i>m. levator anguli oculi medialis</i> (Fig. 7).
Withdrawn and tense stare	The quality of the glance changes to become withdrawn and tense.
Nostrils – square-like	The nostrils are dilated mediolaterally; especially the medial wing of the nostril may be tense. This is most obvious during inspiration.
Tension of the muzzle	There is increased tonus of the lips and tension of the chin resulting in an edged shape of the muzzle.
Tension of the mimic muscles	There is tension of the muscles visible on the lateral aspect of the head, especially <i>m. zygomaticus</i> and <i>m. caninus</i> , but <i>m. masseter</i> may also be tense.

Appendix 3.2

Horse Grimace Scale

Descriptions of The Horse Grimace Scale (Dalla Costa, Minero, Lebelt, Stucke, Canali, & Leach, 2014)

Stiffly backwards ears		
Not present (0)	Moderately present (1)	Obviously present (2)
The ears are held stiffly and turned backwards. As a result, the space between the ears may appear wider relative to baseline.		

Orbital tightening		
Not present (0)	Moderately present (1)	Obviously present (2)
The eyelid is partially or completely closed. Any eyelid closure that reduces the eye size by more than half should be coded as "obviously present" or "2".		

Tension above the eye area		
Not present (0)	Moderately present (1)	Obviously present (2)
The contraction of the muscles in the area above the eye causes the increased visibility of the underlying bone surfaces. If temporal crest bone is clearly visible should be coded as "obviously present" or "2".		

Prominent strained chewing muscles		
Not present (0)	Moderately present (1)	Obviously present (2)
Straining chewing muscles are clearly visible as an increase tension above the mouth. If chewing muscles are clearly prominent and recognizable the score should be coded as "obviously present" or "2".		

Mouth strained and pronounced chin		
Not present (0)	Moderately present (1)	Obviously present (2)
Strained mouth is clearly visible when upper lip is drawn back and lower lip causes a pronounced "chin".		

Strained nostrils and flattening of the profile		
Not present (0)	Moderately present (1)	Obviously present (2)
Nostrils look strained and slightly dilated, the profile of the nose flattens and lips elongate.		

Appendix 4.1

The table is showing the summations of all the comparable questions concerning behaviour in the retrospective study.

Only one of the summations is negative. The rest of the summations are neutral or positive.

Appendix 4.2

Results of evaluation of Equine Pain Face and Horse Grimace Scale

The digits in bold in the results of The Horse Grimace Scale are the ones used for the statistics.

	Equine Pain Face				Horse Grimace Scale			
	Before		After		Before		After	
	Expert	Vet.	Expert	Vet.	Expert	Vet.	Expert	Vet
Horse 1	Not Present	Not Present	Present	Present	3	2	2 (2)	1 2
Horse 2	Present	Present	Not Present	Not Present	(6) (4) 6	8 4 8	(4)	2
Horse 3	Present	Present	Present	Present	(4) (5) (4) (3)	4 5 5 6	(0) (1) 4	1 0 3
Horse 4	Present	Present	Not Present	Not Present	4 (7)	1 7	(7) (3) (2) 4	3 2 2 3
Horse 5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Horse 6	Present	Present	Not Present	Present	- (2)	3 5	(4) 2	4 2
Horse 7	Present	Not present	Not Present	Not present	-	-	-	-
Horse 8	Not Present	Not Present	Not Present	Not Present	(3)	0	2 (3) (3) (5)	2 1 2 1
Horse 9	Present	Present	Not Present	Not Present	- (4) 1 (3)	2 5 1 1	0 (0)	0 0
Horse 10	Present	Not Present	Not Present	Not Present	0 (1) (0)	1 2 0	(1) 1 0 (2) 0	1 1 0 3 0
Horse 11	Present	Present	Not Present	Not Present	6 5 8 7	8 2 9 5	(4) (3) 3 (7)	3 1 2 4
Horse 12	Present	Present	Not Present	Not Present	3 6	0 7	0 (0)	1 1